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ARCTIC TRANSHIPMENT HUB PLANNING ALONG THE NORTHERN SEA ROUTE

POLICY BRIEF

Summary

The Northern Sea Route (NSR) is a geo-strategic maritime route with shorter transshipping times between Asia and Europe. This policy brief discusses transshipment hubs and infrastructure in the Arctic, which are important in unlocking the NSR's full potential and overcoming its logistic, environmental, and geopolitical challenges.

Research on developing Arctic terminals gained pace over a decade with considerable work in Norway, the US, China, and Russia. Logistics and planning dominate the focus, and Russia's ports, such as Murmansk and Sabetta, are central to the NSR's operations. Most, however, lack capacity—including restricted access during winter and poor intermodal connectivity, excluding them from being part of an effective transshipment role.

Transshipment terminals in the Arctic can make resource extraction feasible, deepen connectivity, and stimulate regional development and economy. Challenges, however, include extreme environments, financing, and geopolitical sensitivities. The resolution will require geopolitical coordination, environmentally friendly operations, and investments in developing infrastructure for a commercially feasible role for the NSR in a significant worldwide trading corridor.

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Key Messages

- ⇒ Arctic port development studies have accelerated in the research sample timeframe (2015-2021), showing increasing interest in transshipment routes.
- ⇒ The largest number of research publications on Arctic shipping and the NSR come from authors affiliated with Norway, followed by the USA and Russia, reflecting the academic interest and expertise in these regions.
- ⇒ Russia is the most studied geographical area in Arctic shipping research, accounting for approximately 40% of research outputs, highlighting its strategic importance in the Northern Sea Route (NSR).
- ⇒ Existing terminals in the NSR, including Sabetta, Arkhangelsk, and Murmansk, have important roles but lack infrastructure for servicing larger ships and year-round operations.
- ⇒ Activity in ports varies regionally with different cargo emphasis in different ports. This includes LNG and wood in Arkhangelsk, crude in Cape Kamenniy, and general cargo in Murmansk.
- ⇒ Ports in the Arctic lack critical logistics reliability, including cover with sea ice, poor inland connectivity, and requirements for guidance and icebreaking service.
- ⇒ The NSR provides significant potential for connecting Asia and Europe, but infrastructure development is unbalanced, with a bias towards the western part of the Russian Arctic.
- ⇒ Models for financing terminal development vary, including state-sponsored programs, public-private partnerships, and defence investments.
- ⇒ Transshipment hub development is prioritized in Russia's 2035 Arctic strategy to support LNG shipment and increased cargo volumes in the NSR.
- ⇒ Environmental concerns, including fuel efficiency and reduced emissions, have a key role in determining transshipment hub locations.
- ⇒ New infrastructure projects must integrate with surrounding economic activity, such as extraction, tourism, and community requirements.
- ⇒ Local communities in the Arctic could benefit through increased connectivity through ports, stimulate regional growth and integration.
- ⇒ The increased volumes of shipping and development of terminals must harmonise with social and environmental sustainability and with economic gain.

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Background

This policy brief summarizes a review of research on Arctic shipping (Hermann et al, 2022). Conducted during a period when commercial interest in Arctic shipping routes seemed on the rise, we recognized an increase in studies inquiring about the logistical conditions needed to operate year-round navigation in Arctic waters. This increase in interest was exacerbated by climate change and other events increasing the popularity of the shipping route between the Far East and Europe. Within the larger topic of shipping in Arctic waters, we note that the question of infrastructure emerges several times. However, geopolitical developments in 2022 and the subsequent international sanctions towards Russia have decreased optimism for the development of this route significantly, given that Western shipping companies face difficulties in doing transactions with Russian private and public organizations needed to use the Northeast passage. Then, in early 2025, the subject of Arctic shipping routes seems to gain new traction following the remarks of U.S. President Donald Trump in connection with Greenland's role in the security infrastructure of the Arctic and Chinese and Russian activities. The findings of the review continue to have current value given that the Northern Sea Route (NSR) is part of the Northeast-Passage, and amid sanctions, still has a key role to play in the shipping activities of countries such as Russia and China.

Rising research and policy interest in Arctic Ports

Arctic port development gained significant academic and policy interest in recent years, with 60% of academic studies in this field being produced in the sampled period of 2015-2021. Most studies in this field include logistics (38%) and planning (36%) and, in fact, represent a concern with operational and infrastructure-related concerns in Arctic shipping. In terms of research contributions, Norway leads in the number of academic publications, followed closely by scholars from the USA and Russia. Meanwhile, Russia dominates as the most studied geographical area, highlighting its strategic role in the Northern Sea Route (NSR) and Arctic shipping routes. This research trend underscores the geopolitical and economic importance of Arctic maritime infrastructure, particularly for Norway, Russia, the US, and China.

Infrastructure challenges facing Arctic Ports

Current Arctic port infrastructure, with a focus on the NSR, is not satisfactory enough to enable transshipment operations at a significant level. Most Arctic ports lack deepwater capacities and, therefore, cannot receive larger ships (Pastusiak 2016). Seasonal ice cover reduces operations even further, with most of them not accessible during winter (Faury and Cariou 2016). Others, such as Murmansk and Arkhangelsk, have operational potential for all years but will require significant modernization in position to serve as transshipment terminals (Pastusiak 2016). In addition, a lack of

developed inland transportation infrastructure, such as rails and highways, poses a big challenge in terms of connecting Arctic ports with international value chains.

Strategic importance of the Northern Sea Route (NSR)

The NSR opens a considerable alternative to traditional sea routes linking western Europe and the Far East, reducing between 30–40% in distance between Asia and Europe via Suez. Shorter distance, in theory, can make shipping less expensive, efficient, and resistant in terms of supply chains (Faury and Cariou 2016). However, the route remains highly seasonal due to persistent ice coverage, necessitating specialized vessels and support infrastructure such as icebreakers and advanced navigation systems (Østreng et al. 2013). As shipping times can, in theory, be reduced through the use of the NSR, its demand for operations will demand careful planning and high investment in terms of terminals and logistic infrastructure (Cyr 2021).

Geopolitical and economic drivers of NSR development

The principal developer of Arctic terminals is Russia, and it aims at developing its terminals through infrastructure improvement to serve shipping, such as LNG and containers, by 2035. High-priority developments, such as transshipment terminals in Petropavlovsk-Kamchatsky and Murmansk, form a significant portion of its development nevertheless, political tension and financial sanctions have increased difficulty in collaboration with other nations and investing in shipping infrastructure in the Arctic. Sanctions have restricted access to Western funding, sophisticated technology, and financial markets, and hindered significant infrastructure development (Ng et al. 2018).

Environmental and logistical constraints

Operating in the Arctic presents unique logistical and environmental challenges. Ice conditions require a fleet of icebreakers to facilitate navigation, with Russia currently operating more than 40 icebreakers along the NSR (Sevastyanov and Kravchuk 2020). Icebreakers alone are not the only solution, as most terminals in the Arctic lack proper infrastructure for routine operations. The harsh climate demands significant investment in ice-resistant port terminals, search-and-rescue (SAR) facilities, and emergency response systems. Environmental issues are a core concern, and increased shipping in the Arctic can have consequences such as ocean pollution or loss of habitats from oil spills and other pollution from shipping activities.

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